

cities @ night

10 years

Alejandro Sánchez de Miguel

PLAN-B

UNIVERSIDAD
COMPLUTENSE
MADRID

UNA4CAREER

UNIVERSITY OF
EXETER

Acknowledgments

- Thanks to the astronauts from NASA, ESA, CSA-ASC, ROSCOSMOS, and JAXA who take the images.

- Alejandro Sánchez de Miguel

@pmisson

Every body knows this image. But not every body knows that it is ...

A satellite image of Earth at night, showing city lights and cloud patterns. A large, red, rectangular stamp with a distressed, grunge texture is overlaid on the image. The stamp contains the word "FAKE" in bold, black, sans-serif capital letters, tilted slightly to the right.

FAKE

This is the real image -> a true colour image of the globe does not exist yet

**MEDIALAB
PRADO**

Dark Skies ISS

A. Sánchez de Miguel, J. Gómez Castaño,
D. Lombraña, A. Domínguez, B. Fernández,
JR. Solera, M. Vela, P. Ripolles,
J. Zamorano, J. Gallego y ... 15494 voluntarios
Universidad Complutense de Madrid

Madrid 3 Octubre 2014

**Thanks to the more than
100,000 volunteers**

Response to Invited Commentary

Zhong et al. Respond to “There’s No Place Like Home”

Charlie Zhong*, Meredith Franklin, Sophia S. Wang, and Travis Longcore

* Correspondence to Dr. Charlie Zhong, Keck School of Medicine of the University of Southern California, 1845 N. Soto Street, Los Angeles, CA 90032 (e-mail: zhong@usc.edu)

Initially submitted March 30, 2022; accepted for publication April 25, 2022.

We appreciate the comments by Hauptman et al. (1) highlighting the challenges in understanding how environmental exposures and their inequities contribute to sleep disruptions. The recent interest in how sleep, and the lack thereof, affects human health has led several large cohort studies, such as the California Teachers Study, to include such questions in follow-up questionnaires. We agree with Hauptman et al. that racial equity issues indeed require further interrogation than present in our study (2); even in our cohort, non-Hispanic White participants experienced lower levels of artificial light at night (ALAN), noise, and air pollution and higher levels of green space compared with the rest of the cohort (Table 1). Diverse populations are required to further understand how the role that social and racial disparities affect levels of light, green space, noise, and air pollution and subsequent health effects.

The limitations of satellite imagery in assessing artificial light at night (ALAN) are well known (3, 4), although new technologies and efforts such as those being undertaken by the Cities at Night project led by Dr. Alejandro Sánchez de Miguel (https://citiesatnight.org/) are helping to improve our ability to estimate exposure more accurately at the residential

level. Important measures include light, believed to (4, 5). While we ALAN, we report an estimated 85% (6). Many smart time-dependent and such filtering at least partially (7, 8). The increase across all racial, and more recent features, provide measures of indoor and outdoor exposure for future efforts. metrics, especially substantially from yield further insi

Colour remote sensing of the impact of artificial light at night (II): Calibration of DSLR-based images from the International Space Station

Alejandro Sánchez de Miguel^{a,b,c,d,*}, Jaime Zamorano^b, Martin Aubé^c, Jonathan Bennie^e, Jesús Gallego^b, Francisco Ocaña^{b,f}, Donald R. Pettit^g, William L. Stefanov^h, Kevin J. Gaston^a

^a Environment and Sustainability Institute, University of Exeter, Penryn, Cornwall TR10 9FE, UK

^b Depto. Física de la Tierra y Astrofísica, Instituto de Física de Partículas y del Cosmos (IPARCOS), Universidad Complutense, Madrid, Spain

^c Physics Dept., CEGEP de Sherbrooke, Sherbrooke, J1E 4K1, Canada

^d Instituto de Astrofísica de Andalucía, Glorieta de la Astronomía, s/n, C.P. 18008, Granada, Spain

^e Centre for Geography and Environmental Science, University of Exeter, Penryn, Cornwall TR10 9FE, UK

^f Quasar SR for ESA, European Space Astronomy Centre, E-28691 Villanueva de la Cañada, Spain

^g Astronaut Office, Flight Operations Directorate, NASA Lyndon B. Johnson Space Center, Houston, TX, USA

^h Exploration Science Office, Astromaterials Research and Exploration Science Division, Exploration Integration and Science Directorate, NASA Lyndon B. Johnson Space Center, Houston, TX, USA

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
Artificial lighting
Light pollution
Night
Remote sensing
Urban

ABSTRACT

Nighttime images taken with DSLR cameras from the International Space Station (ISS) can provide valuable information on the spatial and temporal variation of artificial nighttime lighting on Earth. In particular, this is the only source of historical and current visible multispectral data across the world (DMSP/OLS and SNPP/VIIIRS-DNB data are panchromatic and multispectral in the infrared but not at visible wavelengths). The ISS images require substantial processing and proper calibration to exploit intensities and ratios from the RGB channels. Here we describe the different calibration steps, addressing in turn Decodification, Linearity correction (ISO dependent), Flat field/Vignetting, Spectral characterization of the channels, Astrometric calibration/georeferencing, Photometric calibration (stars)/Radiometric correction (settings correction - by exposure time, ISO, lens transmittance, etc) and Transmittance correction. We provide an example of the application of this procedure.

Acknowledgements

1. Introduction

There is growing demand for colour imagery of the Earth at night. This has particularly been driven by increasing recognition of the impacts of outdoor artificial nighttime lighting (from streetlights and other sources) on the natural environment, human health, and associated policy and public concerns (e.g. Rich and Longcore (2013); Hölker et al. (2010); Falchi et al. (2011); Gaston et al. (2012, 2015); Gaston (2013);

We thank R. Moore of the Image Science and Analysis Group, NASA Johnson Space Center for information on ISS cameras and window properties. We thank Lucía García for her help with improving some figures. We also thank the anonymous reviewers for their constructive feedback. This work was supported by the EMISSI@N project (NERC grant NE/P01156X/1), Fonds de Recherche du Québec: Nature et Technologies (FRQNT), COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology) Action ES1204 LoNNe (Loss of the Night Network), the ORISON project (H2020-INFRA-SUPP-2015-2), the Cities at Night project, FPU grant from the Ministerio de Ciencia y Tecnología and F. Sánchez de Miguel.

Cameras were tested at Laboratorio de Investigación Científica Avanzada (LICA), a facility of UCM-UPM funded by the Spanish program

Research using or mentioning ISS data

Our datasets

ISS Papers

MAPS

Cities at Night
concept

Other apps

Gaston KJ, de Miguel AS, 2022
 Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour. 47:373-398

Gaston, K. J., & Sánchez de Miguel, A. (2022).
 Environmental impacts of artificial light at night. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 47, 373-398.

Gaston KJ, de Miguel AS, 2022
 Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour. 47:373-398

Lai, K. Y., Sarkar, C., Ni, M. Y., Cheung, L. W., Gallacher, J., & Webster, C. (2021). Exposure to light at night (LAN) and risk of breast cancer: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Science of the Total Environment*, 762, 143159.

ICFO^R OUTREACH

cities @ night

WHAT IS CITIES AT NIGHT?

TAG

Locate

Georeference

Transfer Learning for Classification of Nighttime Images

Nguyen Minh Hieu¹

The International Space Station (ISS) has taken millions of images of Earth. About 10% of the imagery available from orbit. For technical reasons, we don't precisely know what the ground truth classification algorithm that can correctly identify whether an image shows stars, cities, or other objects.

Files

Transfer Learning for Classification of Nighttime Images.pdf

Transfer Learning for Classification of Nighttime Images

Introduction

This tutorial focuses on [Dark Skies - Classification of Nighttime Images](#)

The goal of this challenge is to use the manually labeled data-set to identify whether an photo shows stars, cities, or other objects. These photographs are used as test set.

Search for Articles:

Journals / Remote Sensing / Volume 14 / Issue 11 / 10.3390/rs14112671

Submit to this Journal

Review for this Journal

Propose a Special Issue

Article Menu

Academic Editors

Martin Aubé

Andreas Jechow

Subscribe SciFeed

Recommended Articles

Related Info Link

More by Authors Links

Article Views 2838

Citations 4

Table of Contents

- Abstract
- Introduction
- Methodology
- Evaluation
- Conclusions
- Author Contributions
- Funding
- Data Availability Statement
- Acknowledgments
- Conflicts of Interest
- References

1<

Open Access Article

Georeferencing Urban Nighttime Light Maps

by Peter Schwind* and Tobias Storch

German Aerospace Center (DLR), Earth Observation Center
* Author to whom correspondence should be addressed.

Remote Sens. 2022, 14(11), 2671; https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14112671

Submission received: 30 April 2022 / Revised: 27 May 2022
(This article belongs to the Special Issue Light Pollution in Urban Areas)

Download Browse Figures Versions

Abstract

Astronaut photography acquired from the International Space Station (ISS) provides a global high-resolution nighttime light (NTL) imagery. Unfortunately, this data cannot easily be used for many remote sensing applications such as urban light pollution analysis, by finding tie points between the reference images and the NTL imagery. To test this approach, we developed an automatic processing chain for the georeferencing of astronaut photographs. The presented processing chain is tested and evaluated by comparing the results with manually identified tie points. The tie points identified in the reference and NTL images are finally matched manually against an independent reference dataset. The georeferencing of high-resolution urban light maps with astronaut photographs are georeferenced with accuracies that are comparable to manual georeferencing. Furthermore, especially for future space-based remote sensing, an automatic georeferencing of high-resolution urban light maps with astronaut photographs will increase and could also be used for quality assessment.

Keywords: nighttime remote sensing; NTL; street network

Find My Astronaut Photo: Automated Localization and Georectification of Astronaut Photography

Alex Stoken¹

alex.h.stoken@nasa.gov

¹Jacobs Technology, NASA Johnson Space Center

Kenton Fisher²

kenton.r.fisher@nasa.gov

²NASA Johnson Space Center

Abstract

Astronaut photography from the International Space Station (ISS) forms one of the longest continuous remote sensing datasets of Earth and has facilitated a large body of research ranging from glacial surface area analysis to volcanic sediment delivery. Such studies are enabled by the geolocation and georectification of the imagery. Yet, localizing astronaut photography of Earth is a challenging and labor-intensive task, tempering the amount of research that can be performed. We present a method for automatically localizing these images named Find My Astronaut Photo, which makes this task feasible by casting the problem as a precision-oriented image similarity and matching exercise.

As the ISS orbits the globe, astronauts can view and photograph most locations on Earth, so there is no pre-computable database of finite landmarks for image comparison. Therefore, we iteratively generate potentially similar images from geolocated satellite imagery on-demand and rely on an image matcher to discriminately detect overall similarity between these images and an astronaut photo.

We evaluate various image matching techniques to find methods which allow us to discretize and reduce our search space to a manageable size, and locate astronaut photographs with high precision and speed.

Find My Astronaut Photo has successfully geolocated over 30,000 photos to date, adding critical location information that increases the downstream utility of the Gateway to Astronaut Photography of Earth (GAPE) database. We also introduce AIMS, the Astronaut Imagery Matching Subset, a new real world evaluation dataset that joins the collection of challenging image matching benchmarks.

1. Introduction

Since the beginning of human spaceflight, astronauts have used handheld photography to share their unique perspective of Earth with the rest of the world. This remote sensing dataset contains over 4 million images that span

Figure 1. Distribution of (a) all astronaut photography by ISS location and (b) geolocated photographs by center point. Only a fraction of all imagery is geolocated. Bins are 10° squares.

more than 50 years, cover most of Earth's landmass, and provide a complimentary and unique dataset for researchers (Fig. 1). The primary differentiator of astronaut observations is also one of its biggest benefits: the method in which the data is collected. In astronaut photography, a trained human is looking through a camera lens at a scene and interpreting the features and phenomena visible, which allows them to react to what they are seeing and adjust for better data collection in real time. While researchers are the primary requesters of imagery, astronaut photography is popular with the general public. The Gateway to Astronaut Photography of Earth (GAPE) receives 30 million visits per month, many of which utilize the image search function to look for photographs of specific locations. While the GAPE database contains photographs from all NASA human spaceflight missions, the majority have been taken from the International Space Station (ISS) due to the spacecraft's 22+ years of continuous crewed operations and the advent of digital camera systems. From low Earth orbit about 415 kilometers (250 miles) above the surface, wide swaths of the planet are visible at all times and even small changes in camera orientation can alter the location depicted in a photo by many kilometers. The microgravity environment and constantly

Batch by Date (n

with 10 ite

HOW WE DID IT?

crowdcrafting COMUNIDAD **PROJECTS** ACERCA pmisson - CREATE YOUR PROJECT

Dark Skies ISS
by Alejandro Sanchez de Miguel

Clasifica esta imagen

Black City Stars Aurora Astronaut None of these No photo No idea

Earth Science and Remote Sensing Unit, NASA-Johnson Space Center. "The Gateway to Astronaut Photography of Earth."

Tweet 0

+31 Recomendar esto en Google

Me gusta Compartir A 11 y a 280 personas más os gusta esto.

crowdcrafting COMUNIDAD **PROJECTS** ACERCA pmisson - CREATE YOUR PROJECT

Lost at Night
by José Gómez Castaño

Do you know about this City?

Save No photo I don't know

Please, be patient with large ISS Images Image Sharp: Good Medium Poor Cloudy: None Less than 50% More than 50%

Use de [+] and [-] buttons to Zoom In and Zoom Out. Press Shift + Left Mouse Button to rotate the image
ISS picture data - Earth Science and Remote Sensing Unit, NASA-Johnson Space Center. "The Gateway to Astronaut Photography of Earth."

Tweet 8 +5 Recomendar esto en Google

Me gusta Compartir A 35 personas les gusta esto. Sé el primero de tus amigos.

HOW WE GOT THE PEOPLE?

- NASA, ESA and other space agencies help us initially.

ESA España @esa_es Siguiendo

RT @cities4tnight: Hoy presentamos citiesatnight.org gracias al proyecto comunidad.medialab-prado.es/es/proyectos/d... de @medialabprado con la colab @esa_es

5 RETWEETS 4 FAVORITOS

13:50 - 9 de jul. de 2014

Responder a @esa_es @medialabprado

NASA NEWS News, features & press releases MISSIONS Current, future, past missions & launch dates MULTIMEDIA Images, videos, NASA TV & more CONNECT Social media channels & NASA apps ABOUT NASA Leadership, organization, budget, careers & more

For Public | For Educators | For Students | For Media Send Share

Space Station 73 186

► Research & Technology
Crews & Expeditions
International Cooperation
Launches & Landings
Ground Facilities
Images & Videos
Space to Ground
Facts & Figures
News & Media Resources
All NASA Missions

Space Station Sharper Images of Earth at Night Crowdsourced For Science August 14, 2014

A wealth of images of Earth at night taken by astronauts on the International Space Station (ISS) could help save energy, contribute to better human health and safety and improve our understanding of atmospheric chemistry. But scientists need your help to make that happen.

The images are available to the public through [The Gateway to Astronaut Photography of Earth](#), the most complete online collection of images of Earth taken by astronauts. This database contains photographs beginning with those taken during Mercury missions in the early 1960s up to recent images from the station, with more added daily. As of August 2014, the collection included a total of nearly 1.8 million images, more than 1.3 million of them from the space station. Approximately 30 percent of those were taken at night.

The photographs taken by astronauts on the station are the highest-resolution night imagery available from orbit, according to William Stefanov, Ph.D., associate program scientist for Earth observations for the space station. Satellites collect data on a more regular basis, but those images typically have much lower resolution. This clarity is possible thanks to the European Space Agency's

North Korea (the dark area) and South Korea at night.
Image Credit: NASA

Other potential applications include evaluating lighting for road and public safety and correlating light pollution with effects on human health and biodiversity.

The atlas is a collaboration of UCM, [Medialab-Prado](#), Spanish Light Pollution Research Network, European Cooperation in Science and Technology's Action Loss of the Night Network, Crowdcrafting, Celfosc and AstroMadrid

NightPod also was used for Crew Earth Observations (CEO) an investigation for which astronauts photographed natural and

IT GOT VIRAL....

the Atlantic

CNN

FOX
NEWS
channel

NBC NEWS

CBS
NEWS

GIZMODO

From *The Atlantic*
CITYLAB

EL CORREO

 Digital
Photography
Review
dpreview.com

rtve.es

la Repubblica.it
Il mondo in diretta 24 ore su 24

EL MUNDO

EVOLUTION OF THE TASKS

Cities at Night

ATLAS OF ASTRONAUT PHOTOS OF EARTH AT NIGHT

Astronauts have been taking photos of Earth for decades (Peit 2008), but the last few years have seen a dramatic increase in the quality of the imagery, particularly at night. Nighime images often have a large public resonance, perhaps because artificial light at night is such a unique signature of human activity on Earth (see e.g. Figure 1). While these beautiful pictures are freely available from a NASA repository (The Gateway to Astronaut Photography of Earth), the sheer number of photos can make finding, for example, an image of a particular city at night a challenge. In many cases, considerable time must be invested in order to find the original data for an image popularised by an astronaut through twitter.

[Full article](#)

← Light pollution

gvSIG →

HIGH-RESOLUTION IMAGERY OF EARTH AT NIGHT: NEW SOURCES, OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

Images of the Earth at night are an exceptional source of human geographical data, because artificial light highlights human activity in a way that daytime scenes do not. The quality of such imagery dramatically improved in 2012 with two new spaceborne detectors. The higher resolution and precision of the data considerably expands the scope of possible applications.

[Full article](#)

ALAN AND CANCER

[Home](#) // [ALAN and cancer](#)[← ALAN increasing](#)

EVALUATING THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN ARTIFICIAL LIGHT-AT-NIGHT EXPOSURE AND BREAST AND PROSTATE CANCER RISK IN SPAIN.

Ariadna Garcia-Saenz, Alejandro Sánchez de Miguel et al.

Environmental Health Perspectives

Among Barcelona and Madrid participants with information on both indoor and outdoor ALAN, exposure to outdoor ALAN in the blue light spectrum was associated with breast cancer [adjusted odds ratio (OR) for highest vs. lowest tertile, OR=1.47; 95% CI: 1.00, 2.17] and prostate cancer (OR=2.05; 95% CI: 1.38, 3.03). In contrast, those exposed to the highest versus lowest intensity of outdoor ALAN were more likely to be controls than cases, particularly for prostate cancer. Compared with those who reported sleeping in total darkness, men who slept in "quite illuminated" bedrooms had a higher risk of prostate cancer (OR=2.79; 95% CI: 1.55, 5.04), whereas women had a slightly lower risk of breast cancer (OR=0.77; 95% CI: 0.39, 1.51). Both prostate and breast cancer were associated with high estimated exposure to outdoor ALAN in the blue-enriched light spectrum.

[Full article](#)

LESSON PLAN

https://zenodo.org/record/3663597#.YFt6xa_0nBR

NATIONAL CHANGES IN NIGHT LIGHT

2,2 %/year

CHANGE IN 500-900 nm RADIANCE DETECTED BY SATELLITE, 2012-2016

LIGHT IS INCREASING EVEN FASTER FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF HUMAN VISION, AS WE SEE BLUE LIGHT (<500 nm) THAT THE SATELLITE CANNOT DETECT.

Kyba, C. C., Kuester, T., Sánchez De Miguel, A., Baugh, K., Jechow, A., Hölker, F., ... & Guanter, L. (2017). Artificially lit surface of Earth at night increasing in radiance and extent. *Science advances*, 3(11), e1701528

EMISSI@N-> 'ECOLOGICAL MONITORING FROM INTERNATIONAL SPACE STATION IMAGES AT NIGHT'

Sánchez de Miguel, A., Bennie, J., Rosenfeld, E., Dzurjak, S., & Gaston, K. J. (2022). Environmental risks from artificial nighttime lighting widespread and increasing across Europe. *Science advances*, 8(37), eabl6891.

Imagen problema

Panama, Panama

cities @ night

CONFIRMAR G

Ninguna de estas

85 mm

ISS030-E-167973

Image courtesy of the Earth Science and Remote Sensing Unit, NASA Johnson Space Center

Images 24,580
 Contributions 122,900
 Users 41,868

RAW

JPG

Figure 2: Response of camera to a uniformly lit screen with stabilized source across all ISOs and times of exposure (T) in seconds. The dispersion of the dots is compatible with the errors of the stabilization (0.5%). Response values expressed in dimensionless units (aka ADU). Data calculated with a D5, although compatible with previously calculated data for D3S. Source: this work.

Figure 7: Original JPG image of Spain used as an exemplar. Madrid (the spider-like lit area) looks to be saturated, although this is not actually the case. This is only one of the reasons not to use JPG images, although geometrically it is equivalent to the RAW image, colours, relative intensities, and other issues like gamma correction mean that this is not recommended.

29

58

87

116

145

174

203

232

261

ISS -Native

ISS -Inter

VIIRS

Imagen problema

85 mm

ISS030-E-237120

Image courtesy of the Earth Science and Remote Sensing Unit, NASA Johnson Space Center

Kiev, Ukraine

CONFIRMAR G

Ninguna de estas

- OpenStreetMap
- Satellite
- VIIRS

Lost at night

ISS046-E-29100

Try Submit Skip

cities @ night

10 years

Alejandro Sánchez de Miguel

UNIVERSIDAD
COMPLUTENSE
MADRID

INSTITUTO DE
ASTROFÍSICA DE
ANDALUCÍA

UNIVERSITY OF
EXETER

Dot Density by Race (1 Dot = 300 People)

- Hispanic
- White
- Black
- Asian

Netherlands

Germany

Belgium

France

India

Pakistan

Egypt

Greek Cyprus

Israel

Turkis Cyprus

Libano

Syria

Jordania

Turquia

